

THE RIPPLE EFFECT: UNDERSTANDING THE IMMEDIATE AND PERSISTENT CONSISTENT OF MEDIA VIOLENCE IN CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT:

This study explores the complex and multifaceted impacts of exposure to violent media content. It tries to understand the immediate as well as the lasting effects that it has on children. Through a comprehensive study and by using phenomenological method of analysis, it examines both the short-term effects—such as increased aggression, desensitization to violence, and fearfulness—and the long-term consequences, including the potential for altered social behaviours and emotional regulation. The research addresses various factors that may amplify or mitigate these effects, such as age, gender, parental mediation, and the frequency of exposure. This study aims to explore how media violence impacts individuals and emphasizes the need for intervention strategies to reduce its harmful effects. The findings underscore the necessity of policy and educational efforts to promote healthier media consumption among children, such as a media diet, fostering environments that support positive development and emotional well-being.

Keywords :- Ripple effect, desensitization, media violence, imitation, aggression, displacement

INTRODUCTION :

Aggression is among the most widespread and harmful behaviors confronting society today. Acts of violence diminish the quality of human life. From murder, kidnapping, and rape to assassination, child abuse, and war—the list of human cruelty appears endless. Children are particularly at risk, of being either the victim or the perpetrator of an act of violence (Maguire and Pastore, 1998). Schools have an equally important role to play in violence prevention because a large portion of children, teens and youth can be reached through schools. Violence is a problem that affects schools directly and an early intervention with students who display aggressive behavior is important. In order to provide intervention, the understanding of the etiology is necessary, which can be multiple in nature. The American Academy of Pediatrics (2001) conducted a study involving parents and youth to assess the negative effects of media messages on the youth. This research showed the media had a wide range of influences on adolescents and children in areas such as aggressive behavior and violence; they concluded that the average American child or adolescent spent more than 21 hours per week watching television. Prime-time television featured between 3 and 5 violent acts per hour, while Saturday morning children's shows contained approximately 20 to 25 violent acts per hour. Internet access and usage in this region of the country has been proliferating year by year, indicating an upward trend in the number of its users across diverse age groups. Information, communication, and entertainment have been some of the key reasons for internet usage. We often do not always hear the clock ticking when we are online and young people are no exception. It's easy to see how kids and young children might lose track of time which affects young people's school work, health and social life. Children of today adopt things with enthusiasm when it represents their space, excitements(Livingstone,2008).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Maguire and Pastore (1998) - Exposure of Children to Violence

Maguire and Pastore emphasized that children are both victims and perpetrators of violence, highlighting the importance of early intervention. Schools play a significant role in violence prevention by addressing aggressive behavior among students.

American Academy of Pediatrics (2001) - Media Exposure and Violence

This study found that children in the U.S. spend over 21 hours a week watching television, with significant exposure to violent acts (3–5 violent acts per hour in prime time, 20–25 during Saturday morning cartoons), raising concerns about long-term impacts on youth behavior.

Livingstone (2008) - Internet Use and Media Habits of Youth

Livingstone pointed out that youth are highly enthusiastic about adopting technology, often losing track of time online. This excessive use affects school performance, health, and social life.

Carnagey, Anderson, & Bushman (2007) - Desensitization to Violence

Their research demonstrated that repeated exposure to violent media reduces emotional and physiological reactivity (e.g., heart rate, perspiration) over time, leading to desensitization where children become emotionally indifferent to violence.

Huesmann (1998) - Social Cognitive Theory and Aggressive Behavior

Huesmann's work explained that children's social behaviors are influenced by situational factors, emotions, beliefs, and learned behavioral scripts. Media violence can contribute to the formation of aggressive cognitive schemas, increasing the likelihood of aggressive responses.

Dodge (1980) - Hostile Attribution Bias in Children

Dodge identified that prolonged exposure to media violence shapes children's worldviews, leading them to interpret others' actions as hostile. This bias increases their propensity for aggression.

Bandura (Social Learning Theory) - Imitation of Violent Behavior

Bandura's famous Bobo doll experiment demonstrated that children imitate observed behaviors. Exposure to media violence increases the likelihood of children imitating violent acts, even when violence is displayed through animated characters.

Gerbner et al. (1980) - Cultivation Theory and Fearful Attitudes

Gerbner's research showed that frequent exposure to televised violence cultivates a perception of the world as more hostile and dangerous. This 'mean world syndrome' leads to heightened fear and insecurity in children.

Anderson & Bushman (2002) - General Aggression Model (GAM)

Their model integrates multiple factors (biological, personality, and situational) showing that violent media exposure increases aggressive thoughts, feelings, and behaviors, and can reinforce existing aggressive tendencies in children.

Paik & Comstock (1994) - Meta-Analysis of Media Violence Effects

Their meta-analysis concluded that exposure to television violence in childhood has a moderate but significant long-term effect on aggressive and violent behavior later in life, with correlation coefficients of .20 to .30.

MATERIALS AND METHODS :

Research Design -

This research used phenomenological approach; 30 students were enrolled for the interview regarding media habits. The interviews were carried out in person and analyzed using Colaizzi's seven-step approach. The use of Colaizzi's 7-step method ensures that the data analysis is systematic, rigorous, and grounded in the participants' experiences. The steps involve: Transcribing the interview data, Initial reading and reflection, extracting significant statements, formulating meanings, clustering themes, describing texture and structure, Providing an exhaustive description and verification. This systematic method ensures the genuine representation of participants' experiences, maintaining adherence to scientific standards.

Study subjects -

The sampling method used was purposive sample. The participants were then briefed about the process of the interview. The inclusion criteria included children who had access to mobile phones and television at home. Once the briefing was done, the formal consent letter was given to the school authorities for their approval & signature. It was clearly stated that the data

would remain confidential and be used solely for research purposes. The participants ranged in age from 9 to 12 years. There was equal division of sample on the basis of gender.

Interview Outline –

The students were interviewed on violence content of media and what were their reactions to them when they first viewed it. How do they feel (in terms of emotions) when they view something of violent content now? What were the long-term effects that they still experience? These responses are considered while discussing the results.

Data collection –

The purpose of the research was briefed to the participants and then the interviews were carried out. For each participants a face-to-face interview was conducted. The time duration for each of the interviews were approximately 30-45 minutes. The participants were allowed to withdraw consent.

Data analysis

Each of the interviews were transcribed and analyses by Colaizzi's phenomenological analysis method. The transcribed data were summarized and meaningful statements were extracted and themes were formulated.

1. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1.1 SOCIO- DEMOGRAPHIC DESCRIPTION:

Fig 1: Type of family

The above figure (1) shows the types of family that the children belong to. 77% of the children belong to nuclear family, 20% lived in a joint family and 3% of the children lived with their extended family away from their parents due to various reasons.

Fig 2: Area of residence

The above figure (2), shows the area of residence of the children. 42% of the children were from urban area, 25% from rural area and 33% belonged to semi urban area.

DISCUSSION

After the interviews were transcribed and analyzed. The following data were retrieved from interviews.

- **Immediate Reaction:** The subjective questions were designed in a way, as to their reactions and experiences of viewing violent content can be understood. When asked to recall the experience after their first violent scene exposure, the reactions commonly mentioned were 'fear, shock, sad', some of the other reactions were 'anger, unpleasant', which were less common. The medium of viewing violent content was television for most of the students. Although due to their age the expressions of their thoughts were not clear but the words used were common to most of the children. Every single response described a negative or unpleasant experience.

- **Present reactions:** The next questions probed into, how they feel now, when they view something violent on television or any other digital platform now, as compared to their previous experience. The common answer was they feel 'okay, nothing, not as much scared as the first time'. Some responses were they still 'feel scared, feels bad, unpleasant, not nice, and afraid'. Though this it was evident that some of the children were desensitized but a majority of them were still taken aback when they viewed something that was gory and violent. There was a sharp contrast noticed in terms of gender, boys said that they tend to feel it is okay and normal. While majority of the girls reported to feeling uncomfortable and unpleasant when they viewed contents with violence.

- **After / Long term effect:** From the above questions, few generic conclusions can be drawn. When asked about their experience, they mentioned about, 'bad dreams, feeling fearful for days, sleeplessness'. Although these are natural responses to exposure to violence, but the exposure to them without supervision and the content being age inappropriate can have varying degree of impact on a child's mind. They may show less emotional response to violence and may accept violence as a way to solve problems in their day to day lives. According to meta-analyses indicate that the long-term impact of childhood exposure to media violence on later aggressive or violent behavior is roughly comparable to a correlation of .20 to .30.(Paik H, Comstock G. and, Anderson CA, Bushman BJ).

From the above discussion, the following themes can be highlighted:

- **Desensitization -**

Desensitization to violence refers to the concept of becoming more tolerant or accepting of violent behavior over time.. Repeated exposure to violence can lead to desensitization, best defined as a reduction in emotional and physiological reactivity to violence (Carnagey, Anderson, & Bushman, 2007). Repeated exposure to violence in any form can lead to habituation and in turn lead to "desensitization". For example: upon viewing a violent scene filled with blood and gore, the initial reaction can be of discomfort, including increased hear rate and perspiration. However, with repeated exposure, this negative response habituates and the child becomes "desensitized" .The child may then be able to observe aggressive behavior without feeling any adverse emotional reactions. . In the Media habits questionnaire, the added questions to gain further insight into the children reaction to violent content revealed that, the children are growing tolerance towards the violent contents that they view in different media platforms. When the question was asked about their reaction now when they see violence now, they wrote that they 'were less afraid, less scared now'. Some said that they did not feel anything and it was quite normal to see violent scenes on screen. Although these shows a certain degree of desensitization that has occurred, there were few who said that, 'it is scary', 'it is not nice'. Children may develop an attitude of apathy. Repeated exposure may also contribute to adolescents' indifference to the phenomena and make them receptive to higher-to-higher levels of violence. The increase in acceptance of violence in adolescents' daily life.

Observational learning /Imitation:

According to widely accepted social cognitive models, a person's social behavior is controlled to a great extent by the interplay of the current situation with the person's emotional state, their schemas about the world, their normative beliefs about what is appropriate, and the scripts for social behavior that they have learned (Huesmann LR, 1998). The theoretical explanation thus provides an understanding of how viewing violence on or off screen stimulates aggressive behavior in the observer/ child. Violence may also be perpetrated through non-human figures (cartoons), but for children's cartoons are also objects of imitation, and they may not be able to distinguish between virtual animated figures and real-life people.

Another important aspect is how screen time is causing displacement. Time displacement effects refer to the role of the mass media (including video games) in displacing other activities in which the child might engage which might change the risk for certain kinds of behavior, e.g. replacing reading, athletics, etc. (Huesmann LR, 1998). In the formative years social cognitive schemas about the world are formed. Prolonged exposure to violence has been found to influence children's worldview, leading them to interpret others' actions as hostile. Such attributions in turn increase the likelihood of children behaving aggressively (Dodge KA). Theoretical explanations about imitation and observational behavior have been extensively researched by Albert Bandura in his famous Social Learning Theory. The bobo doll experiment clearly depicts that children are observant and are absorbent of what is going on in the environment. They are quick to imitate the behavior that is modeled before them. Observing specific social behaviors in their environment makes it more likely that children will imitate those behaviors. Specifically, children who observe violent behavior are likely to imitate it.

• Fearful Attitudes:

The initial reaction of viewing violent content is fearful for most of the children. For most of the children, we have seen that gradually the fear comes down and they become habituated/ desensitized to most of the contents with violent scenes. But it was also observed that for some, the fearful attitude accompanied by nightmares and even bed wetting continues for a prolonged period. This also leads to general fearful attitudes towards the world. They start viewing the real world as more unjust, filled with negative people. Based on the research by George Gerbner and his colleagues (1980), individuals who frequently watch violent content tend to perceive the world as more hostile, frightening, and dangerous compared to those who watch less. When violence is shown being punished on television, it typically leads to a reduction in fear-based perceptions of the real world.

Children's behavioral patterns are yet to be fully formed; therefore, they are more susceptible to get influenced and change by external factors and the long-term effects can be more pronounced, with prolonged exposure allowing them to learn relevant behavioral patterns through violent scenes and adopt them as their own network of patterns. (Li, J, 2023).

Researches in the area of human emotions and its correlation to technology are still raw and not very much penetrated upon. As the technological advancements in the present era 115 expands and reaches to each and every aspect of human life, researchers have newer variables and components to study upon. This will definitely give way to new theory development in the future. After conducting the research for the present variables, the following are some of the points which can be further studied upon.

1. Samples from diverse boards and regions of the state can be included to get a better idea of the use of technology and the psychological variables associated with it.
2. Further research can be carried out using qualitative method as well. As the array of human emotions and the contextual sense can be better understood in the qualitative forms.
3. Various new variables and constructs can be added to the present study and research can be developed.

CONCLUSION :

This study provides valuable insights into the complex and multifaceted impacts of exposure to violent media content on children. The findings suggest that exposure to violent media can have both immediate and long-lasting effects on children's cognitive, emotional, and social development. Repeated exposure to violent media content can lead to desensitization, making children more tolerant of violence. Children may imitate violent behaviors they observe in media, increasing the likelihood of aggressive behavior. Exposure to violent media content can lead to fearful attitudes, nightmares, and a distorted view of the world. Thus, Parents and caregivers should monitor and mediate children's media consumption to mitigate negative effects.

Multidisciplinary Domains

This research covers two domains: (a) Psychology and (b) Mass Communication

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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